

TUTOR AND HIS ROLE IN STUDENT GUIDANCE AS A HELPER AND MENTOR IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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Abstract. *This article examines the role and tasks of a tutor in guiding students, assisting in their learning, and motivating them to recognize their abilities and interests. A tutor is an educator who supports the individual development of students within the disciplines that make up the educational program.*

Keywords: *tutor, educator, student, educational process, individual student development.*

With current educational reforms, new professions and pedagogical specialties have been introduced, one of which is the tutor. Today, "tutor" is a key term in the educational process.

A tutor is an educator who supports the individual development of students within the framework of the disciplines that form the educational program. The tutor's role is to guide students, manage their study plans, assist in learning, and motivate them to recognize their own abilities and interests. While a teacher mainly focuses on delivering the course materials, a tutor employs additional tools like online services and specialized literature.

Today, the education system requires the release of highly qualified specialists, where the main goal is the preparation and need to educate a graduate who will more than once in his life face the need to change his life strategies, professional responsibilities, which at this stage of society's development are replaced situationally, as individual, and not having a regulated "form" [4]. Education cannot but be individualized, this changes the view of pedagogical relations. From the educational model there is a transformation into an accompanying one [6]. Based on the above, the introduction of the principle of individualization of education is more than a pressing issue of our time. Therefore, in the educational environment, today there are prerequisites for the development of tutoring as a pedagogical activity that differs from the work of a teacher in its individualization.

The word "tutor" comes from the English "specialty", which means a guardian, mentor, tutor and teacher. As early as the 12th century, tutoring had a special meaning in English universities. At that time, educational institutions were created on the historical basis of monastic life. Tutoring originated in the oldest universities, such as Cambridge and Oxford. For a long time, these oldest universities served as institutions for training clergy. To this day, they are a model of higher education, when students study and live throughout the entire academic period on campus.

In those days, when there were no educational standards and students were given more freedom, a mentor was needed, a tutor who could help navigate the large volume of educational services provided and compare them with the personal capabilities and needs of the student. By the 17th century, the tutor became the main figure in the educational process. He replaced the professors in organizing individual educational work, students were given the opportunity to choose their own mentor. The tutor chose the volume and range of knowledge necessary for students and independently administered exams and tests based on the results of mastering the materials he provided. He helped in choosing the lectures and practical classes to attend, establishing a dialogue with the student, took part in drawing up an individual plan of study work,

monitored the fulfillment of assignments and professorial requirements, and helped students prepare for exams.

The famous English educator John Locke noted that “The task of a tutor is to develop the child's potential, which would prepare him for his life's work. Tutoring is a process of character formation, building a mindset and body. The goal of a tutor is not so much to teach a child everything that is known, but to educate him in love and respect for knowledge”. During this period, the tutor became a teacher and educator. A tutor is a teacher who supports the individual development of students within the framework of disciplines that form the educational program. Support involves assistance in adaptation, coordination during the educational process, identification of research, entrepreneurial and other creative abilities of students, development of recommendations for career development.

In pursuance of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Approval of the Concept for the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" dated October 8, 2019 and the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 9, 2021 No. 563 "On Measures to Increase the Level of Housing Coverage for Students of Higher Education Institutions of the Republic", according to paragraph 8, from September 1, 2021, the institution of "group curator" for working with students should be abolished, and the practice of assigning tutors who constantly analyze the moral and social state of 1-3 year students of universities and provide direct assistance in solving existing problems should be established. For every 120-150 students, the position of "Tutor" should be included at the expense of 1 full-time unit, and his monthly salary should be equal to the salary of the main position of "Teacher-in-training". In the structure of the Spirituality and Enlightenment Center under the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Specialized Education, a department for the coordination and control of tutor activities should be created, consisting of three state divisions [2].

In higher education institutions, a tutor has a number of responsibilities:

- organizing the process of individual work with students to identify, form and develop their cognitive interests, personal support in the educational space;
- coordinating the search for information by students for self-education;
- joint assessment and distribution of available resources of students to achieve the set goals;
- drawing up individual curricula and planning an individual educational trajectory;
- conducting a reflective analysis of activities and the results obtained together with the student;
- organizing the interaction of the student with other participants in the educational process, promoting the development of his creative potential and participation in project and research activities, etc.

Thus, the main role of the tutor is to maintain the cognitive interest and activity of the student, the most complete realization of his creative potential, and the analysis of development prospects.

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